

Sentinel-2 and Machine Learning Approaches for Early Detection of Forest Pest Outbreaks in Croatia

Luka Raspovič^{1,*}, Branimir Radun¹, Ivan Tekić¹, Iva Odak¹, Ivan Tomljenović¹

¹ Oikon Ltd. – Institute of Applied Ecology, Trg senjskih uskoka 1-2, HR-10020 Zagreb, Croatia, oikon@oikon.hr

* corresponding author

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Abstract: This study presents an ESA-funded project developing machine learning methods for early detection of forest pest infestations in Croatia using Sentinel-2 satellite images. Targeting *Ips typographus* (European spruce bark beetle, ESBB) and *Corythucha arcuata* (oak lace bug, OLB), a multi-temporal TempCNN achieved 96.3% green phase and 94.4% red phase detection accuracy for ESBB, outperforming Random Forest and XGBoost. For OLB, a single-date XGBoost exceeded 99% accuracy. Classification maps at 20 m resolution reached 92.2% (ESBB) and 76.1% (OLB) overall accuracy, validated through area-adjusted error matrices. Key features included red-edge, SWIR, and NIR bands with stress-sensitive vegetation indices.

Keywords: bark beetle; forest pests; machine learning; oak lace bug; Sentinel-2.

1 Introduction

Forest pest outbreaks are intensifying globally due to climate change, threatening carbon stocks, biodiversity, and timber resources. Conventional field surveys are costly, time-consuming, and spatially limited, while Sentinel-2 imagery (10–20 m resolution, ~5-day combined revisit) offers a scalable monitoring alternative. A recent critical review of 26 studies confirmed that Sentinel-2 is the most commonly used sensor for bark beetle green-attack detection, with Random Forest being the dominant classifier (Kautz et al. 2024). Red-edge and water-related vegetation indices discriminate between healthy and green-attacked spruce canopies more effectively with Sentinel-2 than with Landsat-8 (Abdullah et al. 2018). Multi-temporal analysis frameworks have achieved up to 89% overall accuracy for distinguishing wind-thrown, bark beetle-attacked, and healthy forest stands (Candotti et al. 2022), while time-series approaches have enabled early detection of canopy decline in Central European spruce forests (Bárta et al. 2021).

Croatia's forests cover approximately 49% of the national territory and face threats from two key pest species. The European spruce bark beetle (ESBB, *Ips typographus*) causes mass mortality of Norway spruce (*Picea abies*). Infestations progress through the green phase (trees appear visually healthy), red phase (needle discoloration), and grey phase (needle loss). Early detection during the green phase is critical, as the filial beetle generation emerges within 6-10 weeks (Kautz et al. 2024), after which the outbreak spreads uncontrollably. The second target pest is the oak lace bug (OLB, *Corythucha arcuata*), an invasive North American species first detected in Europe in 2000 and since spread to 20 countries (Paulin et al. 2020). OLB feeds on oak leaves, causing chlorotic discoloration

and premature defoliation, with severe infestations reducing photosynthetic activity by up to 58.8%. Differential invasive behaviour between thermophilous and mesophilous oak forests has been documented (Bălăcenoiu et al. 2024). Remote sensing-based OLB monitoring has so far relied on coarser-resolution MODIS data (250 m), which detected persistent late-summer NDVI decreases of up to 14.5% in infested pure oak forests in Hungary and Croatia (Kern et al. 2021). No study has yet employed Sentinel-2 data for OLB detection.

2 Materials and methods

End-user requirements were established through a stakeholder workshop with academia, operational forestry (Hrvatske šume Ltd.), and protected area management. Requirements included minimum accuracy of 70% for early-stage and 90% for late-stage ESBB detection, 90% for OLB, minimum 20×20 m resolution, and spatial-temporal transferability. For ESBB, study areas were Vrbovsko and Plitvice Lakes (Norway spruce), with ground truth from 2019–2020 (92 red phase, 393 healthy polygons). Each red phase ground-truth polygon was annotated with the onset date of the red phase, which was determined through visual inspection of Sentinel-2 imagery. If different parts of a polygon exhibited different red phase onset dates, the polygon was split into multiple segments corresponding to the number of identified onset dates (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Collection of red phase ground truth data for ESBB.

For each polygon, Sentinel-2 L2A time-series datasets of five images at 5-day intervals were collected. The four datasets for each polygon included:

- Red Phase Dataset – five consecutive images, each spaced five days apart, starting from the identified red phase onset date.
- Red Phase Reference Dataset – five images from the same temporal window with same time spacing exactly one year earlier, representing a healthy (non-infested) baseline.
- Green Phase Dataset – five consecutive images, each spaced five days apart, ending just prior to the red phase onset. A one-image buffer was included to

account for possible cloud cover or minor inaccuracies in red phase identification.

- Green Phase Reference Dataset – five images from the same period with same time spacing one year prior to the green phase window, serving as a healthy reference.

Preprocessing included 10 m resampling, cloud masking, and gap-filling. Thirty-four vegetation indices were computed, feature selection via SHAP and permutation importance yielded 18 predictors including vegetation indices such as Disease Water Stress Index (DWSI), Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR), Green Leaf Index (GLI), and Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (ARVI). For OLB, study areas comprised Novska and Okučani (*Quercus robur*) and Psunj Mountain (*Quercus petraea*). Ground truth consisted of 22 polygons ($\approx 14,840$ pixels per class) from June-August 2024. Unlike the multi-temporal ESBB approach, OLB used single-date image pairs (before and after infection), with four vegetation indices. SHAP-based feature selection yielded 5 predictors (Table 1). Outlier detection using Self-Organizing Maps removed pixels exceeding the 99th percentile of quantization error from both datasets.

Table 1. Selected features for OLB classification.

Model	Description
B02	Blue
B04	Red
B05	Vegetation Red Edge 1
RVI	Ratio Vegetation Index
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index

Four ESBB classifiers were evaluated: Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Convolutional Neural Network with Long Short-Term Memory (CNN-LSTM), and Temporal Convolutional Neural Network (TempCNN). TempCNN applies 1D convolutions across the temporal axis through three stacked convolutional layers with batch normalization and ReLU activation, followed by fully connected layers with dropout. Bayesian optimization was used for RF/XGBoost, Optuna (Akiba et al. 2019) for deep learning. Class imbalance ($\approx 5:1$) was addressed through stratified sampling, class weighting, and weighted cross-entropy loss. For OLB, RF and XGBoost were evaluated with 90/10 splits and cross-validation. Classification maps at 20 m were validated using AcATaMa (Llano, X. 2019) in QGIS with stratified sampling for ESBB and random sampling for OLB.

Table 2. ESBB model performance comparison on the test set.

Model	Healthy F1	Healthy Acc.	Green F1	Green Acc.	Red F1	Red Acc.
RF	0.99	100%	0.90	83.3%	0.92	88.0%
XGBoost	1.00	100%	0.95	93.5%	0.94	91.7%
TempCNN	1.00	99.8%	0.95	96.3%	0.95	94.4%

Table 3. ESBB model performance on transferability dataset.

TempCNN	Healthy F1	Healthy Acc.	Green F1	Green Acc.	Red F1	Red Acc.
Before fine-tuning	0.54	42%	0.27	43.5%	0.63	61.8%
After fine-tuning	0.81	68.7%	0.64	85.4%	0.81	89.8%

3 Results

Among ESBB models, TempCNN achieved the highest accuracy, satisfying all requirements. The best hyperparameters derived using Optuna were: 128 convolutional channels, kernel size = 3, 512 fully connected units, dropout rate = 0.3, learning rate = 1.54×10^{-4} , weight decay = 1.24×10^{-4} , and batch size = 64. CNN-LSTM underperformed ($<70\%$) due to spatial imbalance and was excluded. TempCNN outperformed RF and XGBoost on both infestation stages (Table 2), with 96.3% green phase and 94.4% red phase accuracy. The higher green phase accuracy reflects more pronounced spectral changes during the acute initial canopy decline compared to the gradual red phase deterioration.

On the transferability dataset (Plitvice Lakes), the initial model showed poor generalization, with F1 scores of 0.54 (healthy), 0.27 (green phase), and 0.63 (red phase). After fine-tuning with frozen convolutional layers and a reduced learning rate, overall F1 scores and accuracies improved (Table 3). The classification map for Vrbovsko (Figure 2) achieved 92.2% overall accuracy (Table 4). The adjusted area estimates (Table 5) showed that healthy forest dominated the scene (2.55 km^2), while red and green phase infestations accounted for smaller but still measurable areas (0.054 km^2 and 0.222 km^2 , respectively). Coefficient of variation and uncertainty were highest for the infestation classes, especially green phase (28.8%), reflecting greater variability in classification confidence for these categories.

For OLB, XGBoost achieved 99.9% infected and 100% healthy accuracy on the test set, outperforming RF. The optimal XGBoost configuration was: $n_estimators = 180$, $max_depth = 10$, $learning_rate = 0.18$, $subsample = 0.9$, $colsample_bytree = 1.0$, and $gamma = 0.3$. On the transferability dataset (Okučani, *Quercus robur*), it classified 96.7% healthy and 91.4% infected pixels correctly. Robustness testing on sessile oak (*Quercus petraea*) initially showed 100% infected but only 30.7% healthy accuracy, fine-tuning with 10% of new data raised healthy accuracy to 76.1% while maintaining 100% infected. The OLB classification map (Figure 3), generated at 20 m resolution, achieved 76.1% overall accuracy (Table 6). Area-adjusted estimates indicate 24.32 km^2 infected forest ($CV = 6.31\%$).

Figure 2. Classification map of European spruce dominated area around Vrbovsko.

Figure 3. Classification map of oak dominated areas around Novska.

Table 4. ESBB classification map error matrix.

Class	Healthy	Green Ph.	Red Ph.	Total	User's Acc.	
Healthy	57	2	0	59	96.6%	
Green Ph.	12	16	2	30	53.3%	
Red Ph.	2	0	22	30	73.3%	
Prod. Acc.	95.4%	61.9%	68.0%	119	OA:	92.2%

Table 5. ESBB classification map area-adjusted estimates.

Class	Area (km ²)	Error (km ²)	Lower Lim. (km ²)	Upper Lim. (km ²)	CV (%)
Healthy	2.548	0.064	2.400	2.650	2.53
Green Phase	0.222	0.064	0.097	0.347	28.8
Red Phase	0.054	0.013	0.029	0.078	23.5
Total	2.800				

Table 6. OLB classification map error matrix.

Class	Healthy	Infected	Total	User's Acc.		Area (km ²)
Healthy	27	11	38	71.1%		10.07
Infected	22	78	100	78.0%		27.67
Prod. Acc.	55.1%	87.6%	138	OA:	76.1%	37.73

4 Discussion

TempCNN's superior ESBB performance reflects the value of combining temporal and spectral signals for capturing subtle, progressive canopy changes. Its 1D convolutions effectively learn the spectral progression from healthy through green to red phase, consistent with multi-temporal Sentinel-2 bark beetle detection literature (Candotti et al. 2022, Bárta et al. 2021). The higher green phase accuracy supports the hypothesis that the acute healthy-to-stressed transition produces more distinctive temporal gradients in indices like DWSI and NBR than the gradual red phase decline. This is operationally valuable since green phase detection enables timely intervention. For OLB, single-date XGBoost achieved exceptional accuracy, reflecting the distinct spectral signature of OLB feeding damage. The importance of the blue band (B02) is consistent with documented sensitivity of shorter wavelengths to pigmentation changes (Abdullah et al. 2018), while NDVI and RVI capture complementary canopy vigour information. Transferability testing revealed

regional spectral variability for ESBB, underscoring the need for local adaptation. For OLB, strong within-species transferability contrasted with poor cross-species results on sessile oak, indicating species-specific spectral signatures. Fine-tuning proved effective for both pests. For ESBB, the conservative pattern where green phase is overestimated is preferable to missed detections. For OLB, high producer's accuracy for infected areas confirms reliable detection and area estimation (Kern et al. 2021). Limitations include inability to differentiate pest from abiotic damage, insufficient meteorological data resolution, and cloud cover constraints in mountainous regions.

5 Conclusions

This study demonstrated the feasibility of Sentinel-2 and machine learning for early forest pest detection in Croatia. TempCNN achieved classification map accuracy of 92.2% for ESBB, while XGBoost reached 76.1% for OLB. Red-edge, SWIR, and NIR bands with stress-sensitive indices were

most informative. Fine-tuning with 10% local data improved cross-region transferability. Future work should address multiclass frameworks and broader training datasets to support operational early warning systems at national and European scales.

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